

Deliverable 10.1 - Data Management Plan

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	Pedro CAMPILHO (SPI)	Initial draft	08.02.21
0.2	Kate LARKIN (SBE)	EMODnet & data ingest pipeline	15.02.21
0.3	Ward APPELTANS (UNESCO)	OBIS & interoperability	15.02.21
0.4	Stéphane PESANT (EMBL)	Final version	26.02.21
0.5	Daniele Iudicone (SZN)	Review and approval	28.02.21
1.0	Eloïse Trabut (SZN)	Final formatting and editing	28.02.21

2 Executive summary

The present deliverable (D10.1) constitutes the Data Management Plan (DMP) of project AtlantECO. It addresses the European Commission's open access to research data requirements (ORD pilot), as well as Article 29 of the Project's Grant Agreement on the dissemination and exploitation of results. The requirements concern:

- the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information
- data management and preservation
- privacy & security concerns

AtlantECO will generate diverse research outputs, including data and related code, software and scientific articles, about physical oceanography, biogeochemistry, taxonomy-resolved abundances and biomass, biological rates and traits measurements, genomic analyses, numerical model outputs and socio-economic metrics. This diversity requires an ambitious Data Management Plan (DMP), building on existing specialised open science resources that are interoperable and trusted. The DMP follows the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

The deliverable contains the following information:

- A short introduction to the Project's goals, organisation and expected outcomes
- An overview of the Project's data specificities, including their origins (i.e. data re-use & new data collection), types, formats, and purpose
- An outline of the FAIR data management methodology adopted in AtlantECO
- Allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

The AtlantECO Project aims to study the Atlantic Ocean from pole to pole to determine the structure and function of the Atlantic microbiome in the context of ocean circulation and presence of pollutants to assess 1) its role in driving the dynamics of Atlantic ecosystems at basin and regional scales; 2) its potential to act as an indicator of ecosystem status and 3) the mechanism by which it drives the provision of ecosystem services.

In order to deliver this, the Project builds on four activity streams (AS):

- **AS1 - Assess the status of the ecosystem structures, functions, health and services** at regional, basin and all Atlantic scales and provide high quality gridded data products and maps;
- **AS2 - Enhance knowledge and innovate** by adopting standard optical and genetic observations protocols, cutting-edge network analysis methods and better parametrisation of connectivity and biogeochemical models;
- **AS3 - Assess drivers and stressors of change and forecast** their impact on tipping points and recovery of ecosystem structures, functions and services and develop eco-socio-economic models to predict their future states;
- **AS4 - Share and use** capacity and knowledge across the four continents bordering the Atlantic Ocean ensuring a seamless engagement between science, industry, policy and society.

AtlantECO is organised around three pillars of research: **marine microbiomes, plastics and the plastisphere** and **seascape and connectivity**, and focuses on five ecosystem services:

- **ES1:** Climate support system: carbon drawdown and storage
- **ES2:** Deep ocean life support system: transfer of matter & energy to mesopelagic and seabed ecosystems.
- **ES3:** Food security and the trophic fluxes: fisheries and aquaculture.
- **ES4:** Healthy planet, healthy people: biohazards, cycling of plastics and pollutants
- **ES5:** Biodiversity: resilience, adaptation and contribution to the Bioeconomy, including new chemicals

The Project addresses how the three pillars of research, together affect the ecology, biodiversity, sensitivity to climate change and the sustainability of the five ecosystem services. Building on this knowledge AtlantECO will optimize a set of tools and metrics into a unified framework of Eco-Socio-Economic analyses and projections that tightly couple ecosystem functioning and socio-economic activities. This framework will be implemented in a systemic way so that all stakeholders in countries bordering the basin will contribute to the sustainable management of the Atlantic Ocean.

The outcomes of AtlantECO are expected to impact and benefit society on multiple levels, including economic benefits through research-based innovation and new products and services in marine technology and biotechnology, social benefits through education on marine environment and resources, capacity building in the marine sector, food safety and supply from ecosystem services, and environmental benefits through ecosystem sustainability assessments, pollution response and remediation, and tools for marine plastics pollution mitigation. AtlantECO addresses these aspects in a coherent and integrated manner through a comprehensive Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP) and Data Management Plan (DMP).

AtlantECO participates in the Open Data Research Pilot to improve and maximise access to, and re-use of research data, taking into account the FAIR principles and the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information. The present deliverable constitutes the Project's Data Management Plan (DMP).

The Data Management Plan (DMP) will be updated as needed over the course of the Project in order to reflect changes regarding, but not limited to the nature of the data, data sharing policies, and Consortium decisions about new innovation potential, patents and ownership of results.

4 Data Overview

AtlantECO is a data intensive project. It is designed around four Activity Streams (**AS#**) that harness data into the assessment of blue growth potential and sustainable ecosystem services. The first activity stream (**AS1**) assembles georeferenced observations about microbiomes, plastics, the plastisphere, high-frequency carbon flux, and socio-economic statistics. The status of marine ecosystem structures and functions as well as marine ecosystem health and services will be assessed from these observations, and the resulting indicators and indices will be mapped at regional, basin and all Atlantic scales. The second activity stream (**AS2**) enhances the state of knowledge by filling geographic gaps in observations and developing cutting-edge sensor technology to monitor new classes of essential ecosystem variables. Innovations in ecosystem network analysis and connectivity models will generate emerging properties of marine ecosystems, which are tailored to quantify key ecosystem services. The third activity stream (**AS3**) uses multi-decadal time series to assess the drivers of change in essential ecosystem variables using and uses present-day gridded data products from AS1 to predict changes in ecosystem services under future climate scenarios at regional, basin and all Atlantic scales. The fourth activity stream (**AS4**) will provide cost-effective methods to share data and transfer knowledge and capacity to all AtlantECO partners, the wider scientific community, and citizens. While coordinated at all Atlantic scale, methods will be adapted to, and implemented by partners in Europe, South America and Africa. Knowledge will be safeguarded in trusted archives and disseminated via European open access infrastructures Elixir, EMODnet and OpenAIRE.

4.1 Data re-use

Microbiomes observations - AtlantECO will assemble the most extensive 3D biogeography of microbiomes at the scale of the Atlantic Ocean. Our starting point will be the high-quality MARine Ecosystem biomass DATA (MAREDAT¹), which includes historical observations (1960-2010) of microbiomes in the water column based on microscopy counts from oceanographic cruises and the continuous plankton recorder (CPR) survey and based on pigment concentrations (HPLC). AtlantECO will augment this biogeography with recent observations from 2010-2020, providing advanced imaging and genomics analysis of microbiomes taxonomy, biomass, morphological traits, and metabolic as well as ecological functions (Figure 1). These observations are from ten most successful sampling programmes that pioneered marine microbiomics in the last decade (Figure 4); some focusing on surface coastal waters (GOS, OSD and S4S), and the others focusing on high seas from the surface down to the deep ocean. The Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) is remarkable for its yearly, high resolution sampling from North to South and across the two Atlantic subtropical gyres. The Tara and Malaspina expeditions are remarkable for the extent of their imaging, genomics and environmental protocols, as well as their geographic coverage. Geotraces offers concurrent sampling of genomics and trace metals in water, whereas eDNAByss offers concurrent sampling of deep waters and sediments. Finally, the FRAM observatory and ACE expedition provide a good coverage at the boundaries between Atlantic, Arctic and Southern Oceans. Since 2010, the CPR survey is implementing flow cytometry and genetic barcoding analyses on some of its survey lines. These and the standard microbiome CPR observations will be integrated in AtlantECO's gridded data products. Institutions and scientists responsible for all these sampling programmes are partners of AtlantECO, ensuring easy access and quality assurance of all observations, some of which are already available in open access (GOS, Tara, Malaspina and Geotraces), others are about to be published (ACE, eDNAByss, S4S), and some will be sequenced by CEA during the first year of AtlantECO (OSD, FRAM, AMT). Recent observations (last decade) from UNESCO's Oceans Biogeographic Information System (OBIS), from the Global Biodiversity facility (GBIF), as well as from ETHZ's recently published PhytoBase² will also be included.

¹ Buitenhuis et al., (2013) *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, doi.org/10.5194/essd-5-227-2013

² Righetti et al. (2019) PANGAEA, doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.904397

Figure 1. Geolocation of existing observations, samples or profiles that will be assembled and mapped.

Plastics and Plastisphere observations - AtlantECO will assemble an all-Atlantic knowledge base about plastics and the plastisphere at the Ocean surface. Our starting point for plastics will be the review of van Sebille³, with over ten thousand observations collected between 1970 and 2010, albeit restricted to the far West Atlantic (Figure 1). There is no data compilation yet for the plastisphere. Observations from the last decade will be assembled from seven studies conducted by AtlantECO partners in Europe, Brazil and South Africa. With only a handful of studies, the geographic coverage already extends across the Atlantic from East to West and from the Arctic to the Southern Ocean. We will also include recent observations of microbiomes and plastics in aerosols and in surface waters of the seven largest European rivers connected to the Atlantic Ocean, i.e., Thames, Elbe, Rhine, Seine, Loire, Garonne and Tage. We will also collate observations of plastic on the deep-sea floor (in synergy with iAtlantic) and high-resolution, observation-based statistical estimates of terrestrial, riverine and at-sea sources of plastics in the Atlantic Ocean. Moreover, in synergy with four JPI-Oceans initiatives, a wealth of additional knowledge on this topic is expected to emerge at the beginning of the project.

Carbon fluxes observations - AtlantECO will assemble the most extensive 3D mapping of carbon fluxes at the scale of the Atlantic Ocean. Our starting point will be the high-quality compilation of fluxes obtained from drifting and moored sediment traps data in the Atlantic Ocean during 1980-2015⁴. More recent sediment trap data from the fixed ocean observatories FRAM (80°N), PAP (49°N), NOG (24°N) and SOG (19°S) will be added. The core of this activity will assemble high-resolution estimates of carbon fluxes from vertical profiles of all available BGC-Argo floats and ship-born Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP) in the Atlantic from the past three decades. Profiles (0-2000 m) of bio-optical data obtained from BGC-Argo floats and UVP deployments provide the concentration and traits (size, biomass, taxonomy) of particles (including plastics) and organisms in the microbiome (Figure 1). Conversion of these measurements to carbon currency is an obvious source of uncertainty, but growing data bases and validation in the field allow us to work with reasonable confidence intervals. The nature and intensity of the carbon flux can thus be computed at several depths for each profile, hence the proposed 3D mapping. The geographic coverage of these profiles is extensive. AtlantECO will carry out in situ validation of the carbon flux sensors with dedicated in situ measurements on board SV Tara while sailing in the South Atlantic. A neural network-based method will also be used to obtain vertical profiles of bio-optical properties by merging ocean colour (satellite data) and particulate backscattering coefficient obtained from Argo floats⁵.

Ecosystem health and services data - AtlantECO will assemble spatially explicit sets of key marine ecosystem health indices and socioeconomic indicators/stressors that are relevant for the evaluation of marine ecosystem services. Our starting point for ecosystem health is five years of annual assessments of the Ocean Health Index (OHI)⁶ at regional (country) scale and single assessments of the OHI at basin (high seas) and all-Atlantic scales. Relevant indicators will be re-evaluated using AtlantECO's high quality data products about microbiomes, plastics, the plastisphere and carbon flux (WP2), as well as using indicators provided by AS2 such as 2D & 3D maps of gene functions and metabolic pathways generated for epi-, meso- & bathypelagic & benthic ecosystems. Selected ecosystem services will be mapped and assessed by the OHI toolbox using a set of decision tree analyses, non-parametric trend analysis, and reference levels detection methods. Synergy with TRIATLAS will provide a basis for embedding fisheries related data to complement with other datasets (FAO Fishstat; SeaAroundUs) and will provide quantitative linkages with primary production and climatic factors to be embedded into the OHI framework.

³ van Sebille et al. (2015) <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/10/12/124006>

⁴ Torres Valdès et al. (2015) <https://www.earth-syst-sci-data.net/6/123/2014/>

⁵ Sauzède et al. (2016) <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/2015JC011408>

⁶ Halpern et al. (2017) <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0178267#sec002>

Ecosystem drivers and stressors - AtlantECO will analyse time series of in situ observations, remote sensing data, combined (from in situ/satellite synergy) products and model output, including physical, biogeochemical and biological data. The analyses are aimed to identify the main patterns of variability and drivers of changes, to detect extreme events and ecosystem regime shifts. The data considered include the most extensive plankton and carbon flux time series available in the Atlantic. They include the monthly Continuous Plankton Recorder survey over the last 60 years, the annual surveys of Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) for the last 22 years, and fixed observatories FRAM(80°N), PAP (49°N), NOG (24°N) and SOG (19°S) with 10-25 years of sediment trap records across the whole Atlantic. Observation-based products on sea surface temperature, sea level, wind, ocean currents (including vertical velocities), surface photosynthetic active radiation (PAR), mixed layer depth, ocean colour (e.g., chlorophyll-a, net primary production), surface ocean carbonate system (pH, pCO₂ etc.) and nutrients will be obtained from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service and/or from the Copernicus Climate Change Service. The length of the time series based on remotely sensed data depends on the type of platforms included in the retrievals (more than 20 years for ocean colour data, more than 25 years for altimetry, approximately 35 years for thermal data). Finally, physical and biogeochemical model outputs from eddy resolving physical and eddy-permitting physical-biogeochemical hindcast simulations will be analysed. The time series analysis will be based on advanced approaches such as Empirical Orthogonal Function (EOF) decomposition and/or Single/Multi Channel Spectra Analysis (M)SSA, as well as on the analysis of changes in extreme events frequency, intensity, duration, spatial extent, cumulative mean intensity (etc.) and relating them to physical-biogeochemical drivers and stressors. Finally, synthetic observation-based data will be used in addition to carbon fluxes observations to evaluate carbon export variability.

Socio-economic data - Our starting point for socioeconomic indicators/stressors is the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP)⁷ database, which includes projections for population and economic development including age, sex, education, urbanisation and GDP. In addition to the basic SSP socioeconomic elements, the database includes preliminary SSP-based scenarios by integrated assessment models (IAMs). The scenarios provide detailed global and regional projections for energy supply and use, land-use, GHG and air pollutant emissions, average global radiative forcing and temperature change, and mitigation costs. Other drivers and stressors that can influence the exploitation of marine resources (level of technological development and the price of energy sources or food commodities) will be determined in a scenario building exercise whose internal consistency will be optimised using expert opinions, insights from the literature and macroeconomic simulation techniques.

Earth System Simulation data - To predict and evaluate future changes in potential ecosystem drivers, as well as stressors and the response of marine organisms and ecosystems to these changes, we will prepare physical-biogeochemical forcings derived from an ensemble of Earth System simulations (CMIP5 and/or CMIP6 Earth system models, depending on project timing) for low and high emission (socioeconomic) pathways. Earth system model output will have to be phased with observations and corrected for biases arising from incomplete representation of real-world complexity. A statistical correction will thus be carried out on the Earth system model output released during the project for previously identified drivers of ecosystem dynamics, respecting their mean state and variability characteristics, including potential tipping points.

4.2 New observations

AtlantECO will generate new observations from six types of sampling platforms, including public and private research vessels, coastal and offshore observatories, citizen sail boats, and industrial cargo ships (Figure 2).

All-Atlantic flagship cruises - will be organised by AtlantECO partners on board RSS Discovery (UK), Eugen Seibold (Germany), Tara (France), Veleiro ECO (Brazil), Alpha Crucis (Brazil) and the SA Agulhas II (South Africa).

⁷ Riahi et al. (2017) <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959378016300681?via%3Dihub>

They will sample respectively the AMT line across the North and South Atlantic subtropical gyres, the east coast of the North Atlantic, the west coast of Africa, the east coast of South America, the Brazilian shelf, and the GOODHOPE meridional line to Antarctica. Aerosols: In synergy with the Weizmann Institute, research vessels Tara, Veleiro ECO and RSS Discovery will be equipped to sample microbiomes and plastics in aerosols. Rivers: Research vessels Tara and Veleiro ECO will also sample ten rivers in South America (The Amazon, Tocantins-Araguaia, Rio Doce, Sao Francisco and Parana-Rio de la Plata) and West Africa (Senegal, Volta, Niger, Congo, and Orange River), providing an opportunity to assess microbiomes and plastics connectivity between rivers and the Atlantic Ocean. Sampling of aerosols, water and sediments will be conducted in each river, upstream and downstream of its largest city, and databases from our synergy project MicrobioS (ERC Peer Bork, EMBL) will provide a unique link to human gut microbiomes and health in these cities.

The all-Atlantic Ocean Sampling Day - will conduct synoptic sampling at ca. 80 coastal sites bordering the Atlantic Ocean during the summer solstice 2022 and 2023. This activity builds on synergy with OSD, the successful Ocean Sampling Day initiative currently managed with external funding by partner EMBRC-ERIC. AtlantECO will augment this effort both in terms of the depth of sampling & analysis performed, and of its geographic extent, adding ca. 40 sites in South America and Africa to the existing network in Europe and North America.

Citizen Sail for Science - will implement a light version of AtlantECO's standard protocols that will be carried out by citizen scientists along latitudinal and longitudinal sailing routes. This activity builds on synergy with Sail-4-Science, a successful programme, currently managed with private funding by partner SU. AtlantECO will augment this effort both in terms of the depth of sampling & analysis performed, and of its geographic extent, adding 20 sampling lines on a South East Atlantic route to existing sampling routes in the North and South West Atlantic.

A South Atlantic Ocean Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) survey line - will be established for the first time along 3,500 nautical miles transects between Cape Town and Rio Grande in collaboration with the shipping industry. This survey line will start monitoring the biogeography of microbiomes and plastics in the South Atlantic Ocean. The CPR Survey logistics team at partner MBA will negotiate with one of six shipping lines in the region and will coordinate all CPR Survey logistics. Partners in Brazil and South-Africa (FUSP & UCT) will share capacity to do genomics and plastic analyses, and FURG will conduct traditional microscopic analyses.

An all-Atlantic network of Moored Sediment Trap Observatories - will analyse microbiomes and plastics associated with the downward flux of carbon using traditional and novel imaging and genomic methods on sediment trap samples. This activity builds on a recent collaboration between AWI and UKRI, using preserved samples from three fixed observatories in the North Atlantic (FRAM, PAP and CVOO). The geographic coverage of this collaboration will be extended with the analysis of preserved samples from three additional fixed observatories in the Northern Oligotrophic Gyre (NOG; 24°N), the Southern Oligotrophic Gyre (SOG; 18.5°S) and off the Canary Islands (ESTOC, 29°N).

Experimental data - AtlantECO will generate experimental data on board AtlantECO flagship cruises and in aquaculture facilities. Responses to nutrient amendment will be assessed using nutrient-stress-specific active chlorophyll fluorescence, high content fluorescence microscopy, and AtlantECO standard imaging and genetic protocols. Metatranscriptomics in particular will examine the response of genes that are involved in enhancing the formation and remineralization of organic particles and aggregates (TEP formation, sugar degradation, etc). These experiments will help validate and refine predictions of community networks that favour carbon export in the ocean. They will also characterise the quality, amount and functional activity of the sinking organic matter to develop efficient trait-based parameterizations for state-of-the-art biogeochemical models. Experiments with controlled exposure of aquaculture biota to a range of concentrations and types of plastic found in the environment will be conducted to help parametrise models of organisms' exposure to microplastic at local, basin and all-Atlantic scales. Finally, AtlantECO will attempt to measure the biodegradation of nano- to micro-plastics to help parametrise the degradation and transformation of plastics

in dispersion models at local, basin and all-Atlantic scales, and will contribute to bioprospecting activities by screening microbiome strains involved in plastic degradation.

Figure 2. Summary of new observations that will be collected during the project.

5 FAIR data

AtlantECO follows the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The Project has selected data infrastructures specialised in the long-term preservation, annotation and dissemination of five data types: metadata, environmental, genetic, imaging and socio-economic.

Figure 3. Overview of the data infrastructures selected by AtlantECO for the preservation, annotation, modelling and dissemination metadata and four data types: environmental, genetic, imaging and socio-economic.

Data preservation:

- BioSamples (EMBL), the samples metadata archive (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/>)
- EMODnet (SBE), the European Marine Observation and Data network (<https://emodnet.eu/en>)
- ENA (EMBL), the European Nucleotides Archive (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>)
- BioImage Archive (EMBL), the Biological Image Archive (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/>)
- IIASA (third party), the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (<http://www.iiasa.ac.at>)

Data annotation:

- BioSamples (EMBL), the samples metadata archive (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/>)
- MGnify (EMBL), Metagenomics annotation (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/>)
- EcoTaxa (SU), the plankton image annotation platform (<http://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/>)

Data modelling:

- Blue-Cloud (EMBL, SU), the Plankton Genomics Demonstrators (<https://www.blue-cloud.org/>)
- OHI Toolbox (OGS), the Ocean Health Index toolbox (<http://ohi-science.org/>)

Data dissemination:

- OBIS (UNESCO), Ocean Biodiversity Information System (<http://iobis.org/>)
- EMODnet, the European Marine Observation and Data Network (<http://www.EMODnet.eu>)

- EAS, the European Atlas of the Seas (<http://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/atlas/>)

In addition, AtlantECO will use European open access instruments Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) and OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu>) to ensure that all types of data are included in the Project's bibliometrics.

5.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

AtlantECO partner EMBL will support all partners and stakeholders in adopting the highest standard of data curation and will guide them in safeguarding observational and experimental data in selected long-term, free and Open Access data archives. The selected archives provide unique and persistent identifiers (e.g., accession numbers and DOIs), links to related materials, and manual metadata curation that uses as much as possible community standards regarding semantics, formats, units, ontologies and registries. Clear instructions and guidelines will be available on the Project's website.

Metadata about data provenance and environmental context - will be organised and deposited to the BioSamples infrastructure by Project partner EMBL. Specific metadata log sheets, sample identification labels, and 60,000 pre-registered BioSamples unique identifiers are provided by EMBL for AtlantECO's Flagship cruises, citizen Sail-for-Science and all-Atlantic Ocean Sampling Day. Project partner EMBL hosts BioSamples and will be the Project's first-hand contact point regarding this part of the workflow. Cruise Summary Reports (CSRs) will be deposited in open access at Zenodo as soon as possible and no later than three months after the end of the cruise. They will all be deposited as required in selected data infrastructures such as SeaDataNet.

Environmental data - will be submitted by the Project partners to the European Marine Observation and Data network (EMODnet) using the SEANOE-SeaDataNet ingestion platform⁸, or when applicable via already established data submission channels through National Oceanographic Data Centres that are part of the SeaDataNet network. Project partner SBE hosts the secretariat of EMODnet and will be the Project's first-hand contact point regarding this part of the workflow.

Genetics data - will be submitted by the Project partners to the European Nucleotides Archive (ENA) using interactive, command-line or programmatic submission services⁹. ENA is part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) and its contents is replicated and synchronised daily with that of nucleotides archives hosted by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)¹⁰ and the DNA Databank of Japan (DDBJ)¹¹. Project partner EMBL hosts ENA and will be the Project's first-hand contact point regarding this part of the workflow.

Imaging data - will be submitted by the Project partners to the BioImage Archive using the BioStudies submission interface¹². Project partner EMBL hosts ENA and will be the Project's first-hand contact point regarding this part of the workflow.

Socio-economic data - may be submitted by the Project partners to the data repository of the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA DARE), where most of the background socio-economic data of AtlantECO is currently archived. Alternatively, AtlantECO will investigate the possibility of depositing socio-economic data at EMODnet.

⁸ <https://www.seanoe.org/upload/>

⁹ <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide.html>

¹⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

¹¹ <https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/index-e.html>

¹² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/BioImages/help>

5.2 Making data openly accessible

Raw data will be deposited in the selected data archives immediately after being generated and validated. Access may be restricted, but data will become available in open access as soon as possible and no longer than 2 years after the end of the Project.

5.3 Making data interoperable

Data interoperability will be ensured at the point of (1) curating metadata when they are deposited in long-term archives, (2) processing data with analytical pipelines, and (3) generating gridded data products and maps.

Data curation - The long-term archives selected by the Project use a range of standards, ontologies and registers of controlled vocabularies as part of their automatic and manual curation steps, all of which aim at improving data interoperability.

Standards commonly used by the selected data infrastructures:

- Darwin Core - Biodiversity information (<https://dwc.tdwg.org/>)
- ISO19115 - Geographic Information Metadata (<https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:19115>)
- EML - Ecological Metadata Language (<https://eml.ecoinformatics.org/>)

Ontologies commonly used by the selected data infrastructures:

- ENVO - Environmental ontology (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/envo>)
- PATO - Phenotypes and Traits ontology (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/pato>)
- UBERON - Uber anatomy ontology (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/uberont>)
- GO - Gene ontology (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/go>)
- NERC vocabulary services - SeaDataNet common vocabularies that describe sampling devices, parameters, variables, units, etc (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/>)

Registers commonly used by the selected data infrastructures:

- CHEBI - Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/chebi>)
- NCBI Taxonomy - Taxonomic register (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/ncbitaxon>)
- WoRMS - World Register of Marine Species (<http://www.marinespecies.org/>)
- Marine Regions - Place names register (<https://www.marineregions.org/mrgid.php>)
- SeaDataNet metadata services - (<https://www.seadatanet.org/Metadata/>)

The Darwin Core¹³ is maintained by the Biodiversity Information Standards association¹⁴, and is the authoritative standard for publishing biodiversity information. It includes a glossary of terms, identifiers, labels and definitions. Datasets aligned with the Darwin Core glossary of terms can be formatted as delimited text files and packaged as Darwin Core Archives along with a metadata record. A Darwin Core extension is currently being developed with terms from the Genetics Standards Consortium's Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence (MIxS) standard. This extension will be used for adding MIxS terms to Darwin Core aligned datasets. Guidelines for the publication of DNA-derived data through biodiversity data platforms¹⁵ will be carefully considered to improve interoperability between AtlantECO's biodiversity and genetic data infrastructures.

¹³ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.tdwg.org/>

¹⁵ <https://docs.gbif-uat.org/publishing-dna-derived-data/1.0/en/>

Data analysis pipelines - AtlantECO will assemble and (re-)analyse all imaging, genetics, carbon flux, and socio-economic data using state of the art pipelines developed and maintained by partners who are leaders in those fields. All pipelines have in common six steps that improve interoperability: quality assessment, assembly, annotation, storage, visualisation and programmatic access. In close collaboration the project Blue Cloud, these pipelines may be deployed on cloud services that deliver data products directly to the European Marine Observations and Data network (EMODnet). AtlantECO partners EMBL and SU are also responsible for a Blue Cloud demonstrator on imaging and genetics data. Once deployed on the Blue Cloud, our pipelines will benefit from an open science, collaborative platform (BlueBridge) developed by partner CNR, and proposed in AS4 as a capacity building tool for AS1 & AS2 scientists, particularly postdocs in Europe, Brazil and South-Africa.

Imaging pipelines are developed and operated by partner SU in synergy with EMBRC, the European Marine Biological Resource Centre¹⁶, and will be used collaboratively with AS1 & AS2 partners, particularly FUSP in Brazil and UCT in South-Africa. The pipelines were specifically developed to streamline the analysis of images from a range of instruments that will be used in AtlantECO (i.e., FlowCam, ZooScan, UVP and high-throughput microscopy) and to harmonise their data with a common web-based annotation tool (<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/>). Machine-learning models and fast manual curation/validation are implemented in the tool to accelerate image classification into taxonomic or user-defined trait-based groups. The taxonomic backbone is provided by the UniEuk project (<https://unieuk.org/>).

Genetics pipelines are developed and operated by partner EMBL in synergy with ELIXIR, the European research infrastructure for life science¹⁷, and will be used collaboratively with AS1 & AS2 partners, particularly CNRS & CSIC in Europe, UFSCar in Brazil and UP in South-Africa. The pipelines MGnify and META-pipe will be used for metagenomics and metatranscriptomics, respectively. The assembly pipeline includes a decontamination filter and tools for the assembly and read mapping (metaSPAdes and MEGAHIT), binning (MetaWrap) and quality assessment (CheckM). The analysis pipeline varies depending on the type of data, but includes taxonomic profiling using ribosomal rRNAs SSU and LSU (Rfam, mapseq and Silva), ITS1/2 (mapseq, Unite, ITSoneDB) and marker genes (mOTUs). Functional profiling includes ORF detection (Prodigal for assembled data, and FragGeneScan for unassembled reads), InterPro, KEGG orthologs, EggNOG, AntiSMASH, Genome Properties and KEGG pathways analyses. New to MGnify a viral pipeline (VIRify) uses VirFinder and VirSorter to identify both free viruses and prophages. The resulting viral contigs undergo taxonomic classification using a viral profile HMM library.

Carbon flux pipelines are developed and operated by partner SU and will be used collaboratively with AS1 & AS2 partners, particularly PML in Europe, and Argo Regional Centres (ARCs) in Brazil (partner FURG) and South Africa (partner CSIR). Processing of BGC-Argo profiles is done by the European biogeochemical Argo¹⁸ (partner SU) in collaboration with the Coriolis Data Assembly Centre (DAC), and the computation of carbon fluxes is routinely done by partner SU in synergy with REFINE, the ERC Advanced grant of Claustre (SU). Processing of UVP profiles is done by the imaging pipeline (above) and the computation of carbon fluxes is routinely done by partner SU (Guidi).

Ecosystem health and socio-economic pipelines are coordinated by OGS in synergy with OHI¹⁹ the Ocean Health Index initiative and will be used collaboratively with AS1 & AS2 partners, particularly OGS in Europe, FUSP in Brazil and UCT in South-Africa. OGS will partner with OHI developers Halpern (UCSB) and Longo (MSC) to update, improve and integrate new information into the OHI toolbox. The OHI Toolbox is a suite of collaborative, open-source tools for the organization, storage and processing of data, and to model ecosystem “goals”. It is used to calculate and visualize scores of ocean health and associated ecosystem services, therein

¹⁶ <https://www.embrc-france.fr/en/nos-services/plate-formes-technologiques/imagerie/imagerie-quantitative>

¹⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/marine-metagenomics>

¹⁸ <http://biogeochemical-argo.org>

¹⁹ <https://ohi-science.org/>

called “goals”. Calculations and modelling are done with an R package called *ohicore*. The results can be visualized in a Flower Plot for easy communication with a wide audience. Each petal represents one “goal”, and its length with the score of the goal. Each goal is resulting from the integration of status, pressure and resilience indicators and will be updated (also considering microbiomes, plastisphere and information collected in AS1 & AS2).

Data gridding & mapping - Over the last 25 years, the World Ocean Atlas (WOA) has assembled, and regularly updated global gridded climatological data sets of physical and chemical parameters such as temperature, oxygen and nutrients, which rapidly became an invaluable resource to initialise and evaluate global ocean models. Global gridded data sets of biogeochemical parameters such as dissolved inorganic carbon and pCO₂ (SOCAT), and plankton abundance and biomass (MAREDAT) were compiled a decade ago and are now routinely used for the annual assessment of ocean CO₂ uptake made by the Global Carbon Project and for IPCC reports. AtlantECO will produce high quality data products about microbiomes, plastics, the plastisphere and carbon flux in the Atlantic, which will be interpolated on the same grid as the WOA (1° × 1° × 33 vertical levels × monthly climatologies in some cases). Observations will be extrapolated at basin and all Atlantic scales using distribution modelling, i.e., exploiting statistical relationships between observations and environmental data.

Data sets will be compiled in netCDF-4 Hierarchical Data Format Version 5 (HDF5), which is a NASA Earth Science Data Systems (ESDS) community standard that supports geospatial information representing entities and processes varying in time, geographic location and depth. Gridded data products will be managed in a dedicated web-based GIS platform (GEONODE) that will be developed by SBE Belgium, in close collaboration with the EMODnet Secretariat. The GEONODE is an open-source web-based application that will allow partners to upload gridded data products and transform them in GeoTIFF format (Georeferenced Tagged Image File Format). GEONODE will offer discovery and download services. Metadata will be compiled in XML following the INSPIRE Directive guidelines.

5.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

To increase data re-use, the Project’s data will be released with an open data license (CC0, CC BY, or CC BY-NC). Gridded data products and GIS Maps layers will be disseminated to global biodiversity data aggregators, such as EMODnet (managed by partner SBE), the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). Selected maps will also be presented to DG MARE for display on the European Atlas of the Seas. Particular attention will be paid to the preservation of provenance information in the final data products, for example by including all identifiers assigned to data elements by the originators and adding pointers to the respective long-term repositories such as ENA and the BioImage Archive. Depending on the nature of the data and the extent of their metadata, data sets archived at EMODnet may be further disseminated into national data centres and from there into SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, EGDI, or other European data services.

6 Allocation of resources

Four partners (SPI, EMBL, SBE and UNESCO) are allocated a total of ca. 40 PM to implement the Data Management Plan (DMP), and every partner of the Project has effort allocated to their contribution towards open access, dissemination and exploitation of Results. EMBL and SBE are responsible for preserving primary data and gridded data products, respectively. SPI will make sure that all knowledge outputs, other than data are available in gold or green open access at journal publishers, institutional repositories or at Zenodo. EMBL will support all partners and stakeholders with the highest standard of data curation and will guide them in safeguarding observational and experimental data in selected specific long-term, free and open access data

archives. SBE coordinates the EMODnet Secretariat on behalf of the European Commission DG MARE and is responsible for the management, maintenance and further development of the EMODnet Central Portal and the European Atlas of the Seas (EAS). It will ensure efficient dissemination of AtlantECO GIS maps. UNESCO coordinates and develops OBIS and will ensure efficient dissemination of AtlantECO GIS maps. The work is structured in a single task of Work Package 10 and divided into three sub-tasks in the AtlantECO Description of Action as follows:

Task 10.1 Data Management

This task will engage AtlantECO partners in developing data products based on rigorous data management according to the FAIR principles, maximising exploitation and innovation while incorporating the open access principle. A Data Management Plan (DMP) will be launched within the first six months of the project, and continuously updated throughout the project.

Subtask 10.1.1- (SPI) A Data Management Plan (DMP) will identify and specify what data will be open access and provide guidelines for its discovery, access, use, re-use and for its curation and preservation. The DMP will follow the general EU guideline: ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’, regarding research data. The DMP will also specify metadata standards and emphasize the necessity of allocating persistent identifiers for all data. The implementation of the DMP will ensure that outputs are citable and deposited in gold or green open access at journal publishers, institutional repositories or Zenodo.

Subtask 10.1.2 (EMBL) Observations, experimental data, and gridded data products will comply with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. This subtask will support all partners and stakeholders with the highest standard of data curation and will guide them in safeguarding observational and experimental data in selected long-term, free and Open Access data archives (see Section 2.2.2).

Subtask 10.1.3 (SBE) Gridded data products will be managed in a dedicated web-based GIS platform (GEONODE) that will be developed by SBE Belgium, in close collaboration with the EMODnet Secretariat. The GEONODE is an open-source web-based application that will allow partners from WP2&3 to upload gridded data products, transform them in GeoTIFF format (Georeferenced Tagged Image File Format) and serve them as interactive maps (WMS server). GEONODE will offer discovery and download services. Metadata will be compiled in XML following the INSPIRE Directive guidelines. Gridded data products and GIS Maps layers will be disseminated to EMODnet (managed by partner SBE) and the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS; managed by partner UNESCO). Selected maps will also be presented to DG MARE for display on the European Atlas of the Seas.

7 Data security

Several measures have been put in place in order to prevent unauthorized access, modification, replication or destruction of the Project’s data in AtlantECO, including:

Identification security: The security will be assured through identification mechanisms, for granting access to the data stored in online repositories. These will have several layers of security to be implemented in order to protect data of higher sensitivity (users’ personal data, etc.). To face possible unexpected events, and to assure the code continuity, monthly backups of the corresponding repositories will be performed in a backup system by the relevant partners.

Location and workstation security: The partner’s premises will be secured by their own security system and requirements, so the access to the premises of the partners, where all the AtlantECO data files are stored will be secured. Beneficiaries will be asked to use of a password system to remain protected against a possible data breach and advised to use updated antivirus software. Extremely confidential data are to be stored through encryption and sharing information will not be done through personal email.

The Beneficiaries also commit to imposing the data Project policy on all employees, co-workers, subcontractors having access to the AtlantECO data. This policy will include, but is not limited to, allowing copies on local devices only during processing of the data with guaranteed erasure after being processed; extending the access control policies to the local copies; contractual clauses; agreement to terms and conditions before access is granted. Data will be anonymised up to the level required so as to not interfere with the quality of the research.

Ethical aspects

AtlantECO conforms with Horizon 2020 ethical guidelines, including “Data protection and privacy ethics guidelines” and the “Guidance for Applicants on Informed Consent”, these are addressed in detail in the corresponding Ethics deliverable which have been developed and are available to all consortium members. Through these deliverables, the Project’s partners have been informed and briefed about the ethical requirements of the project in conducting, progressing and completing its activities.

The DMP in its iterations will detail how data is stored, who can access it and for how long it can be kept. The consent for data preservation and sharing obtained from data producers, or data owners will be implemented based on applicable license rules. In addition, the relevant information regarding the term of use, curation, sharing datasets which are made available by the data owners will be included in the Project policies that administer Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and copyright management.

These policies will state who will own the copyright and IPR on data to be collected or created, along with the license(s) for its use and reuse. IPR is featured in the consortium agreement with relevant funder, institutional, departmental or group policies on copyright or IPR. When applicable, permissions to reuse third-party data and any restrictions needed on data sharing will also be referred in the associated metadata.